

Enhancing Green Engineering in Western Kenya: Reorienting Mechanical Engineering Courses in Technical and Vocational Education and Training Institutes

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ABSTRACT

United Nations instituted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 1992. Since then, governments across the globe have been under pressure to promote the advancement of a green economic regime in their countries. Green Engineering is a key component of the green economy initiative. To institute a green economic regime, technicians and engineers must be taught the principles of green engineering. Most of the technical manpower involved in green engineering projects are graduates of the Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) Institutes. Initiatives to promote the advancement of green engineering in Kenya must put the TVET sector at the core. The purpose of this study was to examine if mechanical engineering courses in TVET institutes in Western Kenya were green engineering compliant. The TVET institutes based in the four counties of the former Western Province, namely; Bungoma, Kakamega, Busia, and Vihiga, were evaluated. The target population comprised all the principals, trainers, and mechanical engineering students in the 25 TVET institutes in the study area. Sampling was done by the method of multistage random sampling. The sample comprised 13 principals, 75 trainers, and 952 students. Sample size tables of Krejcie and Morgan were used to determine the number of students for the study. The research instrument was a questionnaire. Standardized beta coefficients ranged between 0.247 for departmental compliance with greening principles and 0.447 for availability of government policy on the greening of TVET. All the beta values were statistically significant at a 95 percent level of confidence. There was agreement that government policy on the greening of TVET institutes in Kenya was available. Departmental/college compliance with greening principles was the lowest Performance in green research and green curriculum was moderately good. Implementation of greening of TVET initiatives by the government was stagnating on the ground Targeted incentives should be provided by the government to encourage college principals to implement greening initiatives. Further, resources be availed to college heads to enable them to put in place and implement strategic plans for the greening of TVET institutes

Keywords: Green engineering, Sustainable production, Environmental pollution, Green building materials, Energy efficient

1.0 INTRODUCTION

The world is rapidly transitioning towards a green economic order driven by green engineering (Tukur, 2023). According to Anastas and Zimmerman (2003), green engineering approaches the design of products and processes by applying financially and technologically feasible principles to achieve one or more of the following goals: decreasing the amount of pollution that is generated by the construction or operation of a facility; minimization of human population exposure to potential hazards (including reducing toxicity); improved uses of matter and energy throughout the life cycle of the product and processes; and maintaining economic efficiency and viability. Green engineering can be an overarching framework for all design disciplines (Berawi et al., 2021). Ambrosio-Albala et al. (2023) have defined green building as “the design, construction, and operational practices that significantly reduce or eliminate its negative impact on the environment and its occupants.” Dimitriou et al. (2020) argued that the impacts (both on the environment and humans) of current building materials come about from a reduction in limited material sources, excessive energy use, and the buildup of waste in landfills. According to De Luca, Chen, and Gharehbaghi (2021), the actions creating these issues involve the mining and collection of standard building materials, the preparation and production, the transportation, and the overwhelming creation of construction waste. It is therefore important that the green building itself becomes a necessary focus throughout construction, as accusations aimed at the industry are at an all-time high (Dimitriou et al., 2020; Blackburne et al., 2023).

To encourage the shift towards green engineering and a global green economic order, the United Nations instituted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 1992 (Larsen-Engineers, 2020). Goal number 4 required nations to ensure inclusive and equitable, quality education and the promotion of lifelong learning opportunities for all their citizens. Goal number 6 required nations to ensure equitable and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all. Goal number 7 demanded that nations ensure access to affordable, reliable, sustainable, and modern energy for all. Goal number 8 of the SDG framework demanded that nations promote sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all. Goal number 9 required nations to build sustainable infrastructure, promote inclusive and sustainable industrial infrastructure, and foster innovation. Goal number 13 required nations to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impacts. These SDGs are directly linked to the global green engineering initiative (UNFCCC, 2015). In 2013, the African Union (AU) adopted Agenda 2063 (OAU, 2013). This is the African-domesticated vehicle for achieving the UN’s SDGs. Agenda 2 of the AU’s Agenda 2063 requires members of the African Union to secure a well-educated citizenry and a skills revolution underpinned by science, technology, and innovation (OAU, 2013). This implies that any green engineering training in Kenya would serve to support the nation’s efforts to conform to the SDG and Agenda 2063 requirements (MoE, 2019).

The Paris Accord on climate change mitigation was signed in October 2015 and came into effect in November 2016 (UNFCCC, 2015). Kenya was one of the first countries to ratify this accord. This agreement imposed upon all nations the responsibility of taking extraordinary measures to mitigate climate change and all its effects. UNESCO, the educational arm of the United Nations, in recognition of the role that could be played by the TVET sector in a global transition towards a green economic order, developed guidelines for the greening of TVET institutes (UNESCO, 2017). Although some countries, like the United States, have developed their transition guidelines, most developing countries are relying on the UNESCO guidelines for their transitions (Tukur, 2023). The big question is whether Kenya’s TVET sector is

taking advantage of the availability of these guidelines to facilitate the production of green technicians.

Kenya has realized breathtaking reforms in the TVET sector over the past 10 years (MoE, 2018). Tremendous reorganization in the TVET sector that included the institution of a legal and management framework, among others, has been undertaken. Changes included the reorientation of TVET programs towards competency-based education and training (CBET) (MoE, 2019). This has happened to ensure alignment with regional and international laws, policies, and strategies in the TVET sector. The main aim of the reorganization program was to ensure national conformity with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and the African Union's (AU) Agenda 2063 (GoK, 2007). The United Nations Educational, Social, and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) believes that TVET institutes play an important role in helping make transitions to a low-carbon economy and climate-resilient society (UNESCO, 2016). A low-carbon economy is one whose production activity has the lowest level of air pollution possible. Air pollution attributed to economic activity has been linked to an increasing level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere (Shilenje et al., 2015; Omanga et al., 2014). The increasing level of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere is believed to be responsible for the trends in global warming currently being experienced (Ambrosio-Albala et al., 2023 UNEP, 2014). A climate-resilient society is one that conducts its social and economic affairs in such a manner that there is no permanent damage to the environment and climate change is mitigated. Most of the economic activities that cause climate change are either managed or designed by TVET-trained technicians. If their training is done with a green economy in mind, much of the damage to the environment currently being witnessed across the globe could be avoided. TVET institutes must therefore be placed at the core of the greening initiative (UNESCO, 2017). A greening initiative is necessary to secure a sustainable society. A sustainable society is one in which resources are exploited in such a manner that future generations will not be left with nothing to subsist upon. A sustainable society also avoids the dumping of harmful substances into the environment, thereby securing the sustained habitability of our environment. To develop the technologies necessary for the advancement of a sustainable society, the widespread adoption of green engineering methods is mandatory.

According to Anastas and Zimmerman (2003), green engineering focuses on how to achieve sustainability through science and technology. They recommend a list of 12 principles, which should provide a framework for scientists and engineers to engage in when designing new materials, products, processes, and systems. They add that application of the 12 principles of green engineering should result in products that are benign to human health and the environment (Anastas & Zimmerman, 2003). The TVET input into the development process should be current and relevant for ongoing labor market regulations. The new regulatory regime is strongly tied to the global desire to ensure climate change mitigation. Finally, TVET institutes should be able to instill in their students the consciousness and motivation to develop a green culture (UNEP, 2011). TVET has a role to play in ensuring that the knowledge, skills, and competencies acquired by individuals will enable them to contribute to developing a green economy. It should also ensure that such individuals pursue sustainable practices in other areas of their lives (UNESCO, 2016). The United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP) defines a green economy as one that results in improved human well-being and social equity while significantly reducing environmental risks and ecological scarcity (UNEP, 2011). According to Janicke (2012), the concepts and discourses of the green economy represent a radical transition to more efficient, environmentally friendly, and

resource-saving technologies. This is necessary to reduce emissions and mitigate the effects of climate change. It is also necessary to tackle resource depletion and serious environmental degradation. It is important to note that, according to UNESCO, green engineering goes beyond mere environmental concerns. In its guidelines developed for the implementation of green training in TVET institutes, UNESCO has recommended the adoption of an all-inclusive approach. According to this approach, the production of green engineering technicians can only be effected if the entire college adopts a green culture. A college that hopes to produce green engineering technicians must work on five thematic fronts: greening of the curriculum; physical greening of campus; greening of the surrounding community and the college work environment; greening of TVET; greening of TVET research; and greening of the institutional culture.

It is not clear how effectively TVET institutes in Western Kenya have reoriented their mechanical engineering programs to yield technicians who are competent in green engineering. This study sought to assess if mechanical engineering courses taught in TVET institutions in Kenya were green engineering-compliant. It had four specific objectives: To determine how green mechanical engineering departments in TVET institutions in the Western Region of Kenya are; to assess the availability of Kenyan government policies on the greening of TVET institute campuses in the Western Region of Kenya; to determine how green mechanical engineering research in TVET institutes in the Western Region of Kenya is; and to determine how green mechanical engineering course curricula in TVET institutes in the Western Region of Kenya are. The study restricted itself to the examination of whether TVET institutions had embraced three of the greening measures: greening of mechanical engineering research, greening of mechanical engineering curriculum, and greening of the physical campus environment. The study was anchored on Edwin Locke's goal-setting theory of motivation. It was hypothesized that since college principals and trainers were not involved in the formulation of the national greening policy, implementation of the greening initiative at the college level should stagnate.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

The study was proposed to adopt a descriptive survey design approach relying on quantitative techniques. Several authors (Sarvela & Mc Dermott, 1993; Oso & Onen, 2005; Isaac & Michael, 1990) have recommended the survey approach for studies that involve the exposition of the nature and extent of a specified data set. Additionally, survey design can describe what exists, in what amount, and in what context (Isaac & Michael, 1990). Where economic considerations are important so that data must be collected rapidly and from a small part of the population, Oso and Onen (2005) have recommended the survey approach. The approach is versatile and has been used in works ranging from physical counts and frequencies to the assessment of attitudes and opinions. The target population comprised all the principals, trainers, and mechanical engineering students in the 25 TVET institutes in the study area. Sampling was done using the method of multistage random sampling. The sample comprised 13 principals, 75 trainers, and 952 students. Sample size determination tables by Krejcie and Morgan (1970) were used to determine the sample size for students used in the study. The research instrument was a questionnaire. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics and a linear regression model in SPSS. Any accruing data was analyzed thematically as per the study objectives. This study had one general and four specific objectives. The data was quantitative, so it was analyzed by descriptive statistical methods followed by linear regression analysis. The mean values of the various variables were factored into the

regression model below and run according to the procedure recommended by Pokhariyal (2019) and Namzi and Namzi (2016).

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1X_1 + \beta_2X_2 + \beta_3X_3 + \beta_4X_4 + \varepsilon$$

Where β_0 - is the intercept coefficient; β_1 - represents the explanatory power of the greening of TVET course curricula; β_2 - represents the relative explanatory power of the greening of TVET research; β_3 - represents the relative explanatory power of government policy on the environment; β_4 - represents the relative explanatory power of the greening of mechanical engineering departments; ε - the error term; X_1 : the mean value associated with green curriculum development, external supervision, and quality assurance; X_2 : the mean value associated with the greening of TVET research; X_3 : the mean value associated with the availability of government policy on the greening of TVET; X_4 : the mean value associated with the greening of the mechanical engineering department; and Y : the mean value associated with the degree of reorientation of the TVET mechanical engineering courses to facilitate the advancement of green engineering in Kenya. This model was designed to reveal the extent to which each of the independent variables impacted the reorientation of mechanical courses in TVET institutes towards the advancement of green engineering in Kenya. To run this model, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 29 was used.

3.0 RESULTS

As shown in Table 1a below, the respondent pool had more males than females. Males comprised nearly 67 percent of all respondents, while females made up the remaining 33 percent. As shown in Table 1a, the age bracket between 25 and 30 years of age had the largest number of respondents (45 percent). Most college students are likely to be between 25 and 30 years of age. Since students comprised an overwhelming majority of the respondents, demographic statistics should be skewed towards the age bracket of students. A very small number of respondents were between the ages 31 and 40 (5 percent each for both the 31-35 and 36-40 age groups). A good number of the respondents were above 40 years of age (25 percent). In this age category were students, trainers, and all the college principals. There has been a massive drive by the government of Kenya to attract all adults who have completed high school in the past 20 years but have not acquired any technical training to enroll in TVET institutes. This has been accompanied by a policy of free TVET education. This should explain the presence of students above 40 years of age in TVET colleges in Kenya. One-quarter of the respondents were under the age of 25. This group included a good number of students and even trainers.

The presence of trainers under 25 years of age is explained by the recent recruitment of a large number of Intern University and TVET graduates to beef up staffing in technical training institutes (MoE, 2019). Regarding the work experience of the respondents, a majority had less than 5 years of experience (60 percent). Some 85 percent had below 10 years of experience, and another 10 percent had over 15 years of experience (Table 1a). This was particularly true of the trainees and trainers, indicating that the TVET sector has aggressively recruited trainers in recent years, apparently in response to the recent upsurge in demand for TVET training. Incidentally, a very small number of TVET trainers had between 11 and 15 years of experience (5 percent). This is an indication that there was a period when the TVET sector was not recruiting trainers at all, and sooner or later, this sector will experience a shortage of personnel capable of taking up administrative responsibilities as heads of departments, deputy principals, and college principals. As shown in Table 1(b) below, at least

70 percent of the trainers had a university degree. Of these, 55 percent had an educational degree, while the remaining 15 percent had a degree other than that of education. Another 20 percent of the trainers had diploma-level training. Of these, some three-quarters had an educational diploma, while the rest had a diploma in a technical field other than education. Ten percent of all trainers had postgraduate training. In all, therefore, 80 percent of the trainers had a university degree.

Table 1(a): Demographics of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Female	317	33.3
	Male	635	66.7
Age	Below 25 Years	238	25
	25-30 Years	428	45
	31-35 Years	48	5
	36-40 Years	48	5
	Above 40 Years	190	20
Work experience	Less than 5 Years	571	60
	5-10 Years	238	25
	11-15 Years	48	50
	Over 15 Years	95	10

Table 1(b): Education levels of Trainers and Principals

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Education level	• Diploma in Technical Education	12	15
	• Non-Educational Diploma	4	5
	• Degree in Technical Education	47	55
	• Other Technical Degrees	13	15
	• Post-graduate degree in Technical Education	9	10

3.1 Regression Results

As shown in Tables 2 and 3 below, a number of statistics were evaluated during the process of regression analysis. These included both standardized and unstandardized beta coefficients of the independent variables, the t values, the significance values at a 95 percent level of confidence, and the standard error. The beta coefficients are a measure of the explanatory power of the various independent variables. They reflect the extent to which any independent variable is responsible for a variation in the dependent variable. The dependent variable was the level of advancement in green engineering. The first independent variable was the greening of mechanical engineering departments. Its adjusted beta coefficient was 0.247. The second independent variable was the availability of government policy on the greening of TVET institutes. It had an adjusted beta coefficient of 0.447. The third independent variable was the prevalence of green research in TVET institutions, with an adjusted beta coefficient of 0.371. The final independent variable was the extent to which the mechanical engineering curricula were designed to facilitate the teaching and learning of green engineering. Its adjusted beta coefficient was 0.371. In all circumstances, the standard error values were very low, indicating that the choice of independent variables was good. A low-error term is an indication that the four independent variables almost exclusively and completely explain any variations in the dependent variable. Standardized beta coefficients ranged between 0.247 for

departmental compliance with greening principles and 0.447 for the availability of government policy on the greening of TVET. All the beta values were statistically significant at a 95 percent level of confidence. There was a general agreement among respondents that the availability of government policy on the greening of TVETs in Kenya was a step towards ensuring the advancement of green engineering. Respondents generally felt that departmental or college compliance with greening principles was the lowest. According to the respondents, performance in green research and green curriculum was moderately good at 0.371 each.

Table 2: Analysis of variance (ANOVA)
ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Squares	F	Sig.
1	Regression	1.102	4	.275	.	.b
	Residual	.000	15	.000		
	Total	1.102	19			

a. Dependent Variable: Advancing green engineering

b. Predictors: (Constant), Green departments, green research, green curricula, green policy

Table 3: Regression Analysis
Regression analysis

Model		Unstandardized Coefficient β	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficient β	t	Sig.
1	(Constant)	-1.110E-16	.000		.000	1.000
	Green - departments	.250	.000	.247	176090356.110	.000
	Green policy	.250	.000	.447	324213584.946	.000
	Green research	.250	.000	.371	287616651.810	.000
	Green curricula	.250	.000	.371	290230300.909	.000

3.2 Collinearity statistics of independent variables

Collinearity of variables and collinearity statistics: In regression modeling, collinearity measures the probability that two independent variables of the model measure the same parameter (Pokhariyal, 2019). Where the beta coefficients are statistically significant but the collinearity statistics are beyond tolerance limits, the explanatory value of the independent variables is lost. A collinearity coefficient of 0.8 implies an unacceptably high possibility that a set of independent variables measure the same parameter. As shown in Tables 4 and 5 below, in this study, the choice of independent variables was good. This is because all independent variables showed collinearity statistics that were far below the tolerance limits.

Table 4: Collinearity of variables

		Variable Proportions				
		(Constant)	Green Curricula	Green Research	Green Policy	Green Department
Model	Green Curricula	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
1	Green Research	.00	.89	.00	.07	.00
	Green Policy	.03	.07	.03	.91	.00
	Green Department	.17	.07	.85	.09	.09

3.3 Collinearity statistics**Table 5: Collinearity statistics**

Model		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Tolerance
1	(Constant)	.000	.000	
	Green Curricula	.250	.250	.850
	Green Research	.250	.250	.836
	Green Policy	.250	.250	.730
	Green Department	.250	.250	.707

4.0 DISCUSSION

A good number of respondents felt that the availability of government policy on the greening of TVETs in Kenya was a step towards ensuring the advancement of green engineering. However, a β coefficient of 0.447 means that only 48 percent of the variation in the independent variable is explained by challenges in government policy. There is room for improvement in the area of the availability of government policy on the greening of TVET programs. The degree of compliance at the institutional level was unsatisfactory. Respondents generally felt that departmental or college compliance with greening principles was the lowest. College departments are under the heads of departments, and it is the responsibility of this official to see to it that their departments comply with any government policy. To encourage compliance by the heads of departments, the government should offer them incentives, including sensitization seminars and workshops. According to the respondents, performance in green research and green curriculum was moderately good but not high enough. TVET-based research is largely conducted by trainers and final-year students working on their research projects. By sensitizing both trainers and students to the utility of green engineering, more green engineering research projects could emerge.

Regarding the greening of mechanical engineering departments, respondents generally felt that this is the area in which compliance with greening principles was lowest (β coefficient = 0.247). Greater effort needs to be put in to improve the level of compliance with the UNESCO guidelines at the departmental level. Since departments are run by heads of

departments, the Ministry of Education should organize seminars targeting these offices to enhance departmental greenness. Respondents felt that government policy on the greening of TVETs in Kenya was a step towards ensuring the advancement of green engineering (β coefficient = 0.447). With a beta coefficient of 0.447, this was the best-performing variable. Since the policy environment has been adequately addressed by the government, attention should be refocused on the implementation of that policy at the institutional level. Performance in green research and green curriculum was moderately good (β coefficient = 0.371). Its beta coefficient of 0.371 was about the midpoint between the highest registered (0.447) and the lowest recorded (0.247). There is room for improvement in TVET research, and greater efforts should be made to enhance its greenness. On the greening of mechanical engineering course curricula in TVET institutes, respondents felt that performance was moderately good and about equal to that in research (β coefficient = 0.371). Whereas some progress has been made in the right direction, it is important to make greater efforts to improve the greenness of mechanical engineering course curricula in TVET institutes. Overall, compliance with the UNESCO guidelines on the greening of TVET institutes is satisfactory, but there is a need for the Kenyan government to make a greater effort to promote the implementation of the guidelines, which, according to the college principals, have been delivered to the institutes. All beta coefficients were statistically significant at a 95 percent confidence level. Further, there was very little collinearity between the independent variables, which means that the results are fairly credible.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS

The Kenyan government should provide incentives to encourage both principals and trainers to emphasize the greening initiative and always involve those considered critical to the implementation of any government policy in the policy formulation process. Further studies should be done to determine how the government could involve TVET managers in the formulation of the educational policies they are supposed to implement and provide incentives for trainers and principals to promote the greening of TVET institutes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors harbor no conflict of interest and declare that this article is available for public use without undue hindrance.

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